

CREATION OF AN ELECTRONIC HOSPITAL SYSTEM ON THE C# PLATFORM

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to create an e-hospital to meet the needs of patients with modern capabilities in the field of information technology. Diploma work on raised and solved issues is devoted to the creation of an electronic information system for hospitals.

Methods: The theoretical analysis is based on specific literature and websites, and the comparative analysis is based on existing e-hospital systems.

Scientific innovation: The work is practical in nature. The result is a non-commercial application that can be used by any hospital.

Results: The following problems were solved in the system:

- Existing systems in electronic hospitals have been studied, their working principles have been analyzed, their advantages and disadvantages have been identified and system requirements to the system have been determined;

- a conceptual model of the MsSql electronic hospital was created;

- The operating modes of the system were defined and the software was designed to implement business regimes;

The scientific and practical significance of the work lies in the fact that information technology (IT) develops day by day. Literature related to IT is constantly being improved and updated. Therefore, the creation of an electronic information system for information technology is almost very important. The creation of such hospitals and their connection to the Internet is of special scientific importance.

The system was implemented in the C # programming environment and a user interface was created. The data was stored in the MsSql database and managed by the SqlServerManagement management system.

Keywords: database, C# platform, e-hospital software

Introduction. E-government is the basis of the transformation of public administration into a means of sustainable development. Through innovation and e-government, public administrations around the world can become more efficient, offer healthy services, and meet the demands of transparency and accountability. This document is related to the implementation of the e-health system. E-health is one of the most important areas of e-government. In addition, medical informatics is a growing field at the intersection of public health and business, referring to the information provided by health services and Internet technologies.

The "e" in e-health is not just "electronic" but also a number of other "e" phrases that bring together what e-health is all about: Efficiency, improving quality of care, empowering consumers and patients, sharing information, healthcare scope of service, etc. The statement of this document is to change the traditional paper-based healthcare system in Azerbaijan to a fully electronic system.

Mine matters. The successful implementation of a new system does not only depend on the hardware, the system must also support good enough applications to replace the old procedures. This ensures better interaction of both parties - the system and the users. The system proposed in this paper is developed based on the academic methodology applicable to all AR hospitals in the future. A database and various web applications are used to implement the proposed

system.

A web server offers an interface for users accessing the system over the internet, and a database is used as a storage for data entered by users. An application cannot achieve its goals without a database. But a single database is not enough. Various programming languages, web services and databases are implemented such as HTML5, CSS, JavaScript, jQuery, Bootstrap, PHP, Laravel, MySQL, DataTables, AJAX and Google reCAPTCHA. The mechanism of the proposed system consists of: web page effects (hover, color, focus, resize, animation), PHP, JavaScript and AJAX requirements (PHP and SQL), software requirements (Microsoft Windows 10 operating system, MySQL VB (phpMyadmin), Laravel Framework, Xampp server, DataTables (System Administrator, Services and Patients), non-functional requirements (Security, Reliability and Extensibility), Bootstrap, Web browser and Internet service.

Researched issues. In order to achieve the goal, the subject area was investigated and finding solutions to the following main issues was put in the foreground:

- Create automated administration of hospital processes;

- Providing technical support for the creation of an electronic directory and an electronic hospital;

- To update the website of the hospital and provide general use of the electronic directory here;

- Creating scientific communications through the

Internet;

- Protect electronic information carriers entering the hospital and reflect them in the electronic hospital;
- To prepare scientific book publications of the hospital.

Normative and legislative acts, scientific works of specialists and scientists, statistical information given in the periodical press, and articles of appreciation were used to achieve the set goal during the research.

Research subject. A software cover has been created for work with the electronic hospital.

With the rapid development of technologies, it is possible to store data in electronic form, and these electronic data can be used for business, disease, physician case analysis and other research. EXS / ESS is a step towards the healthcare world where all processes related to clinical data will be automated. It will help to get medical help, inform doctors in time and improve the overall medical system.

EXS is the new wave of this generation due to its many advantages and is the most focused system in the world. Having an EXS / ESS system ensures the privacy and security of information related to healthcare. HIPAA regulations are changing the picture dealing with the privacy and security of electronic health information. One of the main reasons the world is moving towards EXS is to document everything digitally.

A patient registration system is an information system dedicated to the collection, storage, manipulation and preparation of important clinical information about a patient. At the heart of such systems are clinical data, not financial data. Such systems can cover virtually every aspect of clinical data relevant to patient care (eg, a computer-based patient record system). But in the marketplace, EXS is the more popular term. Clinical Record Most systems companies also market their products as EXS products [1].

"Hospital process automation department" carries out the following activities:

- Administration of automated hospital processes;
- Technical support for the creation of an electronic directory and an electronic hospital;
- To form electronic databases;
- Update the website of the hospital and provide general use of the electronic directory here;
- Creating scientific conferences through the Internet;
- To protect the electronic information carriers entering the hospital and deliver them to the users, reflect them in the electronic hospital;
- Preparing hospital publications for printing.

The administration of automated hospital processes is primarily understood as the control of the automation processes implemented in the hospital. This includes constant checking of the internal network, elimination of internal network problems, filtering of information carriers, data protection, optimization and acceleration of Internet use, analysis of the condition of computers, including other technical equipment, and, if necessary, elimination of malfunctions, etc. includes [3,6].

Hospital management programs record payments made in paid services, debts, and also work with any insurance companies. Work with e-hospitals supports electronic information about the disease. Automation of medical hospitals allows to enter information about patients into the computer, and then to transfer (print) it on paper. The electronic hospital system can issue a consultative admission form for each patient. Which will contain these instructions: complaints, description of the disease, current status, diagnosis and treatment plan. Running such a hospital system allows the doctor to diagnose the patient from the ICD database (international classification of diseases). When choosing a diagnosis from the ICD, the hospital program itself tells how to examine and treat the patient [2].

Those working in the hospital program may receive certain access. The administrator who administers the program can change the access permissions or passwords of the employees. Hospital registration and work automation software in hospitals allows the doctor to prescribe his own treatment and examinations to the patient. The hospital's software allows you to save the results of laboratory and ultrasound examinations in electronic form.

Programmatic management will always provide accurate, relevant and up-to-date information. Management security allows you to control all the working processes. The internal plan allows for easy and accurate allocation of funds across all departments of the hospital.

The automated control system formalizes the sending of any report to higher authorities. During work with the program, the motivation of all personnel will be successfully realized. The electronic hospital control system formalizes the necessary analytical control reports. Electronic hospital management software compiles a journal of medical records [4].

Before creating the hospital, we need to get some information about this system. Since this system is a hospital, information about doctors, salaries, departments, patients, rooms, and payments should be given here. Since e-hospital, we need to create a database first. Let's create a database called "HOSPITALDB". There are two ways to create it:

- 1) Using the create database module, which is a special module of Master-pc\Master
- 2) SQL query language create database by typing "VB's name".

After creating an empty data base, it is necessary to fill it with certain tables. Tables can be created in the same way with the special module of Master-pc\Master or the create table command of the SQL query language [5]. As for the hospital we are creating, our database will consist of seven tables. They are as follows:

- 1) Branches – table about branches
- 2) Buildings – table about rooms
- 3) Patients – table about patients
- 4) Payments – Payments table
- 5) Salary – the salary schedule of the staff
- 6) Staffs – table about staff
- 7) Users – a table about users allowed to access the system

After creating the tables in the Master-pc\Master system, if we access the database where they are located, we can see the name of these tables and information about them.

As an example, let's look at the general view of the staff table that we created in the database (Figure 1).

ID	S_NAME	S_SURNAME	S_FATHER_NAME	S_BIRTH_DATE	S_ADDRESS	S_PHONE_NO	S_GENDER	POSITION_STATUS	ACTIVE_STATUS	S_PROFESSION	BRANCH_ID
164	Yegane(Oftalmoloq	Aslanbey	Rufet	1995-03-08	Qara Qarayev 26	774342082	F	Head Doctor	A	Oftalmoloq	1005
165	Cahid(Cerrah)	Hasimov	Arif	1965-03-17	Neftciler pros	517702545	M	Doctor	A	Cerrah	1009
166	Ekber(Ginekoloq)	Ehli	Musa	1978-12-18	Neimanov ray ...	502657898	M	Doctor	A	Ginekoloq	1025
167	Rahim(travmatoloq	Pashayev	Sebuhi	1955-11-08	Mastaga qes	774892512	M	Doctor	A	Travmatoloq	1022
168	Gulnare(onkoloq	Qedimelyeva	Pasa	1970-03-11	Lokbatan	552366646	F	Doctor	A	Onkoloq	1030
*	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL

Figure 1. General view of the staffing table in the database

By combining the tables I created in the Database diagram, I get the following result (Figure 2)

Figure 2. View of the base diagram

Before creating the program structure, let's first clarify the internal structure of the hospital. The hospital project I created is managed by the IT engineer as a program, and used by the Chief Doctor and the Receptionist. Thus, the chief doctor and the receptionist perform certain operations by entering separate program windows by entering their username and password [7]. (Figure 3-4)

Figure 3. Program login window

Figure 4. The main window of the program and other menus

Figure 5. Patient registration page

Conclusion

Scientific studies were conducted on the subject area, existing systems were analyzed. The points that I was not satisfied with in the structure of the existing systems were reflected in the software of the e-hospital system that I created.

The development of the program went through the following stages:

- information about the subject was collected and analyzed;
- demand for the e-hospital system was discovered;
- the software of the e-hospital system was developed;
- a web page was created to provide detailed information about the hospital's activities.

As a result, the development history of the e-hospital, the study of the subject area in different countries, the program-controlled e-hospitals and their creation priorities are reflected.

The establishment of the infological and conceptual model of the database, the implementation of design issues in the subject area, the creation of the e-hospital database in the MS SQL program were reflected.

The processes performed in the e-hospital program that I created are reflected. They are: adding a new employee to the system through the program, editing or deleting data from the database, checking the amount of income in the system on a daily basis and at any intermediate dates, and creating and restoring a security password for new program users, registering patients, editing data, examination-operation processes accepting payments and arranging appropriate rooms

for inpatients can be carried out.

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